

W.E. DISTRICT

Smart and local renewable Energy

District **heating** and **cooling**
solutions for sustainable living

22

Partners

9

Countries

4

Demosites

10

Technologies
developed

14.973k

EU funding

Start:
Oct. 2019

End:
March 2023

Context

Heating and cooling of buildings in EU accounts for 50% of total energy consumption.

70% of this energy is generated from fossil fuels.

Objectives

The overall objective of the project is to demonstrate district heating and cooling (DHC) as integrated solutions that exploit the combination of

- renewable energy sources,
- thermal storage and
- waste heat recycling technologies

to satisfy 100% of the heating and cooling energy demand in new DHC and up to 60-100% in retrofitted DHC.

WEDISTRICT solutions will integrate

Solar Thermal Technologies

- Parabolic Trough Collector
- Fresnel
- Tracking concentrator for fixed tilt collector

Biomass Technologies

- Low emission biomass boiler
- With additional Bag Filter DeNOx Technology

PV-Geothermal System

- Hybrid solar geothermal district heating system

Cooling from Renewable Energy Sources

- Renewable air cooling unit (RACU)
- Advanced absorption chiller

Data Center Waste Heat Recovery

- Recovery of waste heat with fuel cells

Molten Salt Thermal Energy Storage

Advanced Digitalisation

4 demo sites

WEDISTRICHT technologies will be implemented in **4 real-scale projects** in Spain, Romania, Poland and Sweden.

Luleå

Excess heat integration in existing District Heating

Bierutów

Non-renewable District Heating retrofitting

Alcalá de Henares

New District Heating and Cooling network

Bucharest

Retrofitting of an inefficient District Heating section

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Contact us

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Our Partners

Coordinator:

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